

D1.1 Data Management Plan

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Executive summary

This deliverable describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected processed and generated during the VitiGEOSS project. The purpose is to establish how the data will be created, stored and backed-up, who owns it and who is responsible for the different data and which data will be preserved and shared.

It will cover, the handling of research data during and after the project, what data will be collected, processed, or generated, what methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open and how and how data will be curated and preserved. The Data Management Plan will be used as a standard data guideline for the project consortium to ensure interoperability and sharing for public data generated by the project.

Each project partner should respect the policies set out in the resulting Data Management Plan. Datasets have to be created, managed, and stored appropriately and in line with European Commission and local legislation. Dataset validation and registration of metadata and backing up data for sharing through repositories is the responsibility of the partner that generates the data. The datasets in the repository project will be preserved in line with the European Commission Data Deposit Policy.

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Introduction

This document presents the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the VitiGEOSS project. This deliverable, the VitiGEOSS data management plan, describes the research data that will be collected and generated during the project and explains how it will be exploited or if it will be shared for verification and re-use.

The VitiGEOSS project aims to use of European Open Earth Observation services for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental, and local level. To do so, the project will develop an innovative vineyard management solution based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors with the objective to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

This process is visualized in figure 1, on the left all data inputs are displayed in green, satellite data, climate models, fixed cameras, infield measurements and end-user information.

Figure 1. VitiGEOSS project data flow visualization.

This Data Management Plan will describe how all data will be managed, during the project and after it is finished. **Data management** refers to the everyday handling and workflow of research data during the active phase of a project as well as the practices that support long-term preservation, access, and use after the project has been completed. These activities can include planning, documenting data, formatting data, storing data, anonymizing data, and controlling access to data.

There are different stages in the data management planning which are of importance and have influence on how the data will be collected, used and stored. The stages as a cycle are displayed in figure 2.

Figure 2. Data Management Across VitiGEOSS Lifecycle

Discovery & Planning: This is the stage to determine what existing datasets can be of use in the VitiGEOSS projects and which will have to be produced. Also, how to combine existing datasets or analyze existing datasets; identify privacy, confidentiality, and other ethical issues; consider documentation format and content and the metadata standards to use to describe the data; identify potential users of project data; identify an appropriate data repository to archive the data; and determine data management costs.

Initial Data Collection: This is the stage during which to determine workflows and procedures for organizing files, backups, and storage, performing quality assurance protocols, and setting appropriate access controls and security measures.

Preparation & Data Analysis: The collected data may not be the right fit to be in input right away, it may be needed to clean, manipulate, or process the raw data. What is important during this stage is to document the changes to the raw data and creating a “master” version to be analyzed and eventually archived. It is also essential to document analysis procedures such as additional modifications to the data, the model used, the code used to run the analysis, and hardware and software specifications.

Publication and Sharing: This is the stage to consult with the archive or repository to determine file formats, clean and further document data. Additionally, all documentation should be reviewed to ensure that they contain enough information to allow the data to be re-used by a third party.

Long-term Management: During this stage researchers share their data and findings through publications, submit reports, and deposit data and supplementary materials into the archive or repository.

The Data Management Plan will be updated during the project lifetime, new versions of the DMP could also be created whenever significant changes arise in the project such as: new data sets, changes in the consortium policies and external factors.

1. Data collection

The VitiGEOSS data consists of multiple inputs from different sources over a period of three growing seasons. To ensure the accurate management of those different data streams the Data Management Plan is set in place. The VitiGEOSS system will be designed work with multiple data sources, decreasing risk of lack of data. If one data source is not available it can easily be replaced with another one. Additionally, the focus lies on Mediterranean areas in which cloud cover is low during the grape production season.

Besides the use of GEOSS and Copernicus data, data will be collected three vineyards during the course of the VitiGEOSS project. In Portugal the Quinto do Ataíde vineyard of the Symington Family Estates will be testing possible solutions, in Italy the Mirabella Eclano Estate owned by Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl will serve VitiGEOSS as a validation scenario, and in Lleida, Spain the Torres family vineyard.

1.1 VitiGEOSS data

The purpose of the VitiGEOSS data collection is to provide forecasts, estimations, and recommendations to wine makers to optimize vineyard management processes. The innovative solution promoted by the project has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which requires to intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigate the effects of climate change, reduce negative environmental externalities, and promote local economic growth.

The three research plots are located in important European viticultural regions (Douro, Portugal; Taurasi DOC areal, Italy; and Juneda, Lleida, Spain). Each pilot plot will be of a minimum size of 1 ha and will be managed according to the specific protocols adopted commercially by the end-users for wine making. This approach will allow to validate VITIGE OSS in different climate conditions, different cultivars, and viticultural strategies (different vineyard management protocols and different wine style goals).

The first six months of the VitiGEOSS project are used to select suitable plots at the three demo sites. The main selection criteria will be: vineyard exposition and slope; the cultivar; the intra-vineyard homogeneity (vines with similar age, vigor, rootstock, and training system; homogeneous soil; etc.); availability of a nearby weather station; availability of phenology data on the specific cultivars and availability on historical management data. Once the pilot plots are identified, the setup of the pilot plots will finish when the installation of the fixed cameras in the field; irrigation system adaptation if needed, installation of machinery data-loggers, acquisition of specific field equipment, etc.; and the necessary vineyard modifications will be implemented.

The activities of the second task aim to fine-tune the calibration of the models included in VitiGEOSS. During the first vegetative season of the project, a high-quality dataset collected in the three selected vineyards will be used to tune the calibration of (i) the downscaled weather forecast models (ii) the phenological stage prediction models, (iii) the key crop indicators tracking models, (iv) the vine disease early warning system forecast, and (v) the business and sustainability manager. An additional fine-tuning of the models will be realised between the vegetative seasons two and three.

The quantitative data resulted from all services will be provided in-season for operational use by end users via the VitiGEOSS portal in an automated way with the right frequency according to nature of the different services:

- Weather: daily, weekly and monthly
- Phenological: daily and monthly (field-based)
- Crop status: weekly, (field-based)

- Disease: weekly & daily on critical episodes (field-based)
- Sustainability: weekly/ (on demand) for optimization and plan of task and resources, monthly for sustainability indicators. (by using the appropriate parameters from the services)

The second and the third vegetative seasons of the project will be dedicated to fully validate the Intelligent Services that will run operationally, using data collected at the three demo sites. The performance of the VitiGEOSS services will be monitored, making special emphasis on the validation of the business and sustainability services as well as the related dashboard (as final application integrating several intelligent services outputs) to confirm they could help the winemaking community to improve their current strategies in order to be more sustainable.

Data collected during second year will be used to calculate intermediate performance of intelligent services and proposing improvements to be implemented in the third year.

Data from the third year will be used to calculate final performance of the intelligent services. This will be done by evaluating the capacity of the tool in:

- forecasting the vine phenology
- monitoring the key crop indicators
- forecasting the occurrence of vine diseases
- delivering precise disease treatment recipes
- optimizing the use of resources and tasks
- evaluating sustainable indicators and implementing sustainability practices

1.2 Standards and methodologies

All data files need to be labelled and organized in a systematic way in order to make the data accessible for current and future users. As well as the naming of the files, this will happen according to agreed conventions.

The data will be collected by the service providers; they can upload and download data with VitiGEOSS services. The service providers will collect, store, and maintain the data, the standards will be different depending on the provider. A survey was conducted to collect information on methodologies used by the different service providers. The survey can be found in Annex A.

1.3 Best practices for file formats

Service providers will deliver data in an agreed upon format, the main formats are as followed:

Table 1. File formats organized based on output.

Output	Format
Numerical data	Time series, excel, csv
Images	Images (e.g., jpeg)
Key crop indicators	JSON
Phenological phases	geoTIFF, csv, JSON
Alerts, messages	Text, JSON
To be confirmed	JSON, XML, csv

In table 2 below you find more detailed information regarding the data which will be collected by service providers Eurecat, BSC and LINKS.

Table 2. Service providers Eurecat, BSC and LINKS, type of data and format.

Service	Type of data collected	Type of data Generated	Data format
In-field repository	Machinery data from tractors and sensors on sprayers, weather stations data images from fixed cameras, Drone images, historical data about (, weather stations, yield, disease treatments, phenological stages)	Machinery data from tractors and sensors on sprayers, weather stations data images from fixed cameras, Drone images, historical data	Time series; excel, csv, json xml files, images
Disease management	<p>Weather stations: real time data and historical data (Temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind)</p> <p>Weather forecast</p> <p>Historical and real treatments (date, dose, product used)</p> <p>Weather and climate (seasonal and sub-seasonal) forecasts</p> <p>Real and forecasted phenology stages and dates</p> <p>Zonal delineation and crop health indicators</p> <p>Sprayers data</p> <p>Copernicus data</p>	<p>Disease risk assessment, alerts</p> <p>NNMB/MONARCH NCEP CFSv2 ECMWF SEAS5</p> <p>Polygons and variable rate/risk maps for disease treatments</p>	<p>Text messages</p> <p>NetCDF Grib2</p> <p>JSON data</p> <p>GEOJSON data</p> <p>XLS, CSV files</p>
Business and sustainability manager	<p>Data from farm information systems (Pesticides, fertilizers, irrigation water, human labour, tasks scheduled)</p> <p>Weather and climate (seasonal and sub-seasonal) forecasts</p> <p>Yield and harvesting date forecasts</p> <p>Machinery data</p>	<p>Task schedules</p> <p>Resource usage recommendations</p> <p>Sustainability KPIs</p>	<p>JSON, XML</p> <p>XLS, CSV files</p>

The size of the data is dependent on many factors such as the frequency, resolution, area size and more. Some data components are updated daily and provide information every three hours, others are checked weekly and give daily output. Not all data is collected by use of devices, surveys and interviews with end-users and potential stakeholders are also an important knowledge base for the project. Data formats are flexible to change when agreed upon.

2. Ethics and legal compliance

All beneficiaries involved in the VitiGEOSS project strive for balance and equal opportunities, this is related to gender, age, nationality, etc. Attention has been paid to a balanced distribution of gender, age and country of origin in composing the advisory board and the consortium.

Data collection, storing and possibilities of sharing in the future are to be agreed upon by all beneficiaries who are part of the VitiGEOSS project. These agreements are part of a later process within the project and a more elaborate answer will follow.

Subtask 3.2.1: Set up the API service store to establish connections with the individual service providers. Negotiate standards between partners. This task finishes when project partners communicate with the services in the API service store, sharing data and services between them and adhering to the standards used in the VITIGE OSS portal.

3. Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues

The VitiGEOSS Project will produce data assets such as an application portal; Task 5.2. This task will oversee the management of all intellectual property that will arise from the project and will take the necessary steps to ensure that it can be appropriately protected. IP experts from EUT will support partners in the identification of Exploitable results - a project results table will be developed to identify, synchronize, and conduct efficient IP planning and management, including ownership rights. Exploitation managers will be assigned to each result and the management of the collective project foreground will be a part of periodic reporting and project meetings. IP strategies - Regular patent surveillance will be undertaken in relation to relevant exploitable results. This will allow a correct management of future patentability processes (e.g., confirm novelty, inventive step, industrial application) and ensure “Freedom to Operate” for future commercial products/services.

During the project there are 42 months to improve the existing models with EO data, and validate them during 3 vegetative seasons demonstration in end-users’ plot. Nevertheless, special agreements may be done with end users (Symington, Mirabella Eclano Estate and Torres) for a longer fine-tuning of the platform.

4. Sharing the data and OPENDATA

Data sharing among partners throughout the project is done by using SharePoint and THREDDS.

During the term of VitiGEOSS, Zenodo will be used to share the public results with those interested. Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository which contains scientific publications and data. Sharing data and making the research as open as possible can be realized through this, the Zenodo page for VitiGEOSS is: https://zenodo.org/communities/869565_vitigeoss/.

The aim of the VitiGEOSS project is to use European Open Earth Observation services for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental and local level. The commercial innovation and market penetration is work package 5, first an extensive market assessment will be conducted. Followed by a market analysis and competitive assessment, focusing specifically on the wine sector in Europe. Critical success factors and other outcomes of the first steps will form for the assessment of the VitiGEOSS potential market acceptance. This process and its results will determine in what way the data will come together and could be shared.

5. Roles and responsibilities

All nine parties in the VitiGEOSS project have their own role and responsibilities during the course of the project. These roles and their responsibilities are all documented in the ‘Description of Action’ of the VitiGEOSS project.

Each partner is responsible for the data generated from his/her institution as data producers, proper data collection, documentation, and storage throughout the duration of the project, under the supervision of their respective data protection officers. Specific agreements may be signed among partners in order to grant access to the different datasets for the different uses.

The VitiGEOSS platform is a complex project with the intervention multiple actors with different data inputs, an exhaustive analysis regarding the data management procedures will be conducted further in the project.

Table 3. List of beneficiaries and their role in the VitiGEOSS project.

Name	Lead beneficiary for WP	Role
Eurecat	WP 1: Project management, WP 2: Intelligent (information) services on vineyard management	Service Provider
Fondazione Links		Service Provider
Symington Family Estates		End-user
eLEAF	WP 3: Integrated Vineyard Management Application Portal (DSS)	Service Provider
Barcelona Supercomputing Center	WP 6: Communication & Dissemination	Service Provider
Price Waterhouse Coopers /Ag - Assessoria de Gestao	WP 5: Commercial Innovation and market penetration	Service Provider
Universita Degli Studi Di Napoli Federico II	WP 4: Demonstration	Service Provider
Aziende Vinicola Michele Mastroberardino SPA		End-user
Miguel Torres SA		End-user

All partners are responsible for the treatment of the data on their own premises, all partners have their own security measures in place to avoid any possible treads. In a later stadium of the project data will be shared through the use of an API, standards and methods will follow.

6. Storage and security

The service providers will collect, store, and maintain the data, the standards will be different depending on the provider.

Data will be stored in a safe environment that only allows authorized personnel to access. This is controlled with the support of password protection, verified IP addresses and by recording access to servers. Backups will be taken periodically, and a restoration process is established in case of a failure.

7. Annex A

Project Number 869565
Project Acronym VITIGE OSS
Project title Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Please answer the following questions for VitiGEOSS project:

Name:
Company:

1. Data Summary

What types and formats of data will you generate/collect?

What is the origin of the data?

What is the interval of the data?

What is the expected size of the data (per interval if relevant)?

2. Data specifics

What naming conventions do you follow?

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Specify if not standard.

How will you share the data, via which service?

Is previous research used in the data set, if so, specify?

3. Responsibilities

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

